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Historical Sciences

PROTECTION OF FAMILY VALUES IN MODERN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article discusses the goals and objectives for the protection of family values in modern Russia. It is shown that the modern Russian reality can be characterized as an extremely complex and responsible period, the leading features of which are the formation of a market economy, social stratification in society, and a change in spiritual and moral foundations. Particular attention is paid to the socio-economic transformations of society that affect the practice of everyday life, as a result of which there is a change in social relations, including in the sphere of the family, family policy, as well as social protection of motherhood and childhood, since in the difficult socio-economic conditions of our time the most young families become vulnerable.

Keywords: family, person, value, society, state.

I. INTRODUCTION

The solution of serious social problems in the field of population can be carried out only if there is an effective system for providing assistance and support to the population (mothers, children, adolescents, youth, families). And in this context, more and more often, researchers studying the problems of the modern family say that there is a decline in the social potential of the family, the prestige of family values, an increase in the number of divorces and a decrease in the birth rate, an increase in crime in the sphere of family and marriage relations, an increase in the risk of children being exposed to deviations in development due to the unfavorable psychological climate in the family. In this regard, key aspects of the social protection of the family, motherhood and childhood have now become the subject of heated scientific discussions. These discussions are complicated by the lack of a unified conceptual framework and theoretical and methodological grounds for considering the problem, which reinforces the need for a theoretical search for constructive directions for its further development. The appeal to the historical analysis of social protection as a social phenomenon is relevant, which determines the need for understanding and public reflection in the public consciousness of the negative processes associated with the family crisis. A dysfunctional or socially maladjusted family is, without a doubt, a mirror of the general socio-economic ill-being. Exploring it in a sociological vein, we get an adequate picture of the state of society as a whole.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the article is the dialectical-logical, structural-functional methods of cognition, the methodology of system analysis. Of particular importance is the institutional approach, which makes it possible to study the key social phenomena in the subject area chosen by the author and show their fundamental nature for the development of society.

The study of the problems of social protection of motherhood and childhood in the context of the transformation of society was carried out on the basis of the fundamental works of A.I. Antonova, S.I. Goloda, T.I. Zaslavsky, S.G. Kirdina, M.S. Mackovskosh, S.Y. Naumova, L.I. Savinov, R. Skinner, D.Z. Kleese, D.G. Kharcheva, N.M. Chernyak, P. Sztompka and some others.

III. DISCUSSION

When analyzing the current state of the institution of the Russian family among historians and demographers, two points of view on its prospects can be distinguished: the first is pessimistic, according to which the traditional Russian family is disintegrating and the state of the family institution is considered as a crisis (A.I. Antonov, V.L. Arkhangelsky), the second is optimistic (A.R. Volkov, V.M. Medkov), which is shared by the author of the article and which reveals the institution of the family in changing forms and functions.

An important place in the study of the family is occupied by the study of the problem of the position of a woman, a woman - a mother, a woman's self-preserving behavior, which can be expressed by the general concept of "motherhood". The changes that have taken place in society have weakened the traditional functions of the family, the regulative nature of sexual morality in the distribution of responsibilities in the family, have affected the social status of women, made her generally more active and independent.

The problems of motherhood were studied in the works of V.B. Bodrovoy, A.V. Borodin, V.A. Borisova, T.A. Gurko, O.G. Isupova, A.R. Mikheeva and others. In the works of these scientists, various aspects of motherhood are considered, due to socio-economic conditions, the standard of living of the population, changes in value preferences and attitudes of modern Russian women.

In historical science, the problems of childhood are traditionally studied within the framework of the demography of families, the sociology of education, in the context of analyzing the problems of interaction between the broad social environment and the system of education. During the crisis of state institutions of socialization and state policy in the field of education and upbringing, traditional cultural institutions take on the main role. The growing role in these conditions begins to play the family, to a greater extent preserving the elements of cultural tradition, social and moral security of the child.

General problems of childhood in the conditions of modern society and in the conditions of transforming Russia are considered in the works of A. Arefiev, I.S. Kona, E.M. Rybinsky, S.N. Shcheglova, B.Y. Elkonin.

IV. RESULTS

One of the serious problems currently facing Russian society, and Western civilization as a whole, is the crisis of the family as the basic social institution of society. The progressive deterioration of the state of the family in all aspects of its life - from family and marriage relations of spouses to raising children, from solving material problems to caring for elderly parents, is not only the result of current events, but also a generalized process that goes back to the beginning of the 20th century. In modern Russia, this process is exacerbated by the atmosphere of a general protracted crisis associated with the result of the transformations of recent

decades. The development and spread of this process was superimposed by such negative realities of post-reform Russia as the low standard of living of the population, mass alcoholism, drug addiction, the growth of aggressiveness and cruelty in society, etc. Unfavorable demographic trends, which themselves are generated and fed by the difficult state of the family, including the state of motherhood and childhood, are of decisive importance.

The radical reforms being carried out in modern Russia, which affected literally all spheres of society, led not only to positive changes, but even more caused phenomena of a socially negative nature. deep economic crisis, social anomie, destruction of moral ideals and guidelines. As a result of their actions, a whole range of acute social problems has developed in the area we are studying: an increase in the number of children born out of wedlock; social disorganization of families; unhealthy relationships between family members; malicious deviations from the duties of raising children, etc. Hence, of course, the growth in the number of abandoned, neglected children, child drug addiction, crime, prostitution and other socially negative deviations in the children's and youth environment.

As for the family, all of the above problems can be focused in the concept of a "socially maladjusted family", which has gained acute relevance in modern Russia. Family trouble has turned from a sad particular case into an attributive characteristic of a huge number of Russian families. And this cannot but affect the state of society and its institutions, since trouble in the mass of families generates trouble on a social scale, since the demographic situation in the country, the development of the physical and spiritual forces of a person depend on the success of the family in fulfilling its basic functions.

Russia, having declared itself as a welfare state, has defined the creation of conditions that ensure a decent life and free development of citizens as the main goal of its social policy. However, as the practice of recent decades shows, in the context of the transformation of society, Russian families turned out to be the most vulnerable and socially unprotected by the state. Accordingly, a sharp drop in the standard of living, a deep differentiation of incomes, inflation and rising prices, as well as fundamental changes in the labor market required fundamentally new approaches in the formation of a system of social protection for the family, motherhood and childhood, adequate to the new socio-economic conditions.

Currently, there is a complex process of replacing the old system of social security, benefits and compensations with a new system of social protection of the population, which is being formed in the course of market economic and social transformations in the country. But this process cannot be recognized as perfect and complete, since it is far from always justified and is still in the stage of its formation. In addition, these changes were complicated by the negative consequences of the destruction of the previously created social infrastructure and the beginning of the "withdrawal" of the state from the social sphere.

Of particular importance to social protection is the need to maintain the political stability of society as an important factor in national and economic security, on which the prospects and results of the planned transformations depend. The system of social protection and the process of its reform are interconnected with socio-political changes and fundamental changes in the economic complex of the country, which can create conditions and resources for its development.

The system of social protection being created in the country made it possible, to one degree or another, to mitigate the consequences of economic and political transformations and prevent social explosions.

In modern society, the family still creates the most comfortable conditions for motherhood, parenthood and parenting. Therefore, only awareness of the social threats that depopulation brings with it, only the development and implementation of family policy, the purpose of which will be the revival of a full family with several children in new social conditions, can stop depopulation. It is the familistic paradigm that allows the social protection of motherhood and childhood to be transformed from a policy limited by momentary problems into a holistic and, most importantly, adequate to the strategic objectives of the country's social policy.

V. CONCLUSION

The social problems of motherhood and childhood are now being promoted to the rank of the most important national tasks, on the solution of which the fate of the country depends. At present, the number of children in Russia is 30 million, of which about 620 thousand are disabled; 9 million children live in poor families (with incomes below the subsistence level, i.e. outside the framework of ensuring physical survival); about 3 million children are in a state of neglect and homelessness; about 5 million children are brought up in incomplete families with all the ensuing consequences; about 1 million children are characterized by antisocial behavior, including alcoholism, drug addiction and crime.

The list of these figures allows us to imagine the specific dimensions of the social disaster that threatens the well-being and future of Russia. Accordingly, a holistic system of socio-economic and legal measures is needed to address the priority tasks of children's livelihood, including improving their quality of life, protection from violence and cruelty, the consequences of various kinds of conflicts and creating a favorable environment for the development of children.

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ЗАЩИТА СЕМЕЙНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются цели и задачи по защите семейных ценностей в современной России. Показано, что современную российскую действительность можно охарактеризовать как чрезвычайно сложный и ответственный период, ведущими чертами которого является становление рыночной экономики, социальное расслоение в обществе, изменение духовно-нравственных устоев. Особое внимание уделено социально-экономическим преобразованиям общества, влияющим на практику повседневной жизни, в результате чего происходит изменение общественных отношений, в том числе в сфере семьи, семейной политики, а также социальной защиты материнства и детства, поскольку в сложных социально-экономических условиях современности наиболее уязвимыми становятся молодые семьи.

Ключевые слова: семья, человек, ценность, общество, государство.

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